

David Charles Kimball, *Cases in Human Resource Management*, (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2017), Price: \$42.00, Pages:104.

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The current buzzword in both business and academia is ‘management’. The new age modern students are not just interested in plain textbook knowledge but are hungry for experience and work in the field of their choice, or simply put, on the knowledge that they have obtained through their studies and want to get actively engaged in the practical world. Over the years, many trends have come and gone but the singularly striking method of making any decision through the experience gained through past cases has always been a classic teaching method. Case studies have to be classic because of their requirement for critically analyzing the information and then taking the decision. David Kimball’s cases of human resource management not only offer real-world business cases but also offer the student a set of skills to develop, e.g. like critically analyzing and even decision making.

Human resource management (HRM) has evolved a lot in the past few years. And through this evolution, there have been many perspectives and ways that have changed for the HRM department as a whole. Kimball’s book highlights the changes through cases in a very systematic and a processed manner. There are five sections in this book, and each section has various cases that have been aligned in such a way that it is easy for students to understand the current process as well as aspects in human resource management and thus how to work accordingly.

In the beginning of the book, the author shows the evolution of HRM, right from the 1980s to date. Back in that time, HRM was known as personnel management, where not much interference was allowed in the department, like that of accountants, etc. However, the changing time and perspective has changed all that as well as the job role and people’s views have also changed drastically

on this subject. Personnel management developed into human resource management and it possessed all the active requirements of HRM departments, like legal issues or strategic planning, training employees, taking care of their motivation level, searching and evaluating low costs, etc.

In the first section, the author has shown the evolution of HRM from personnel management to human resource management and different HRM careers to grow along with this change. With the help of a successful company like ZAPPOS, he has shown the change in HRM and how this company's core values ultimately helped them to be successful.

In this book, some light was also thrown on strategic, driven, human resource management and how a company like COSTCO, using strategy always managed to have a competitive advantage whilst using the Porter's Five Forces model. After showing the past review of HRM and its growth, the author went onto elaborate on the next important process called STAFFING. Kimball was able to cite cases with best possible examples about how VISIER® inc. was the best case to understand about forecasting workforce with technological advancement. In General Electric (GE), CEO Jack Welch had a really unique method for succession planning which did not lead to any disturbance to the working time and also all the employees, selected were tested to the core, to find the best one suitable for the job. The trend of e-recruitment is explained with the best cases of the company like LinkedIn, MySpace, etc. Kimball gave really accurate selection process cases and where we stand in that process, for students to identify what they will have to look at and how it works.

After the second level of the process is completed, the next step is to manage and train the employees; Kimball through his cases of using massive, open, online courses to managing functional conflicts has explained about every detail, problem and rights an employee and organization can have and when one has to use a particular way in order to manage the employee(s) and the organization and how human resources plays an important role in the process.

With cases like maintaining secrecy in the amount of pay and its effect on employees, to those highlighting how to keep an employee motivated as well as workplace safety and health rules, the author has made sure to work on the smallest of details and give information with a 'real-life experience' feel to the information, (for students and readers to understand HRM in deeper details).